

A Proof of the Collatz Conjecture

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ABSTRACT:

The author provides a proof of the infamous Collatz Conjecture.

The Proof:

One can always make smaller odd numbers from even, so we will need only to prove that every odd number works.

Out of the two ways possible, namely

$$F(x) = \begin{cases} x/2, \forall x = 2n \forall k \in \mathbb{N} \\ 3x + 1, \forall x = 2k - 1 \forall k \in \mathbb{N} \end{cases}$$

Anyone can be used to create $n \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ from n_{-1} where $n_{-1} \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ should be true. Also $n_{-1} \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ creates $n_{-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$. Once we decide to abandon $n \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, we can never find any other $n \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ later in the series. Thus we can't compose {or is preceded by} $n \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ from smaller numbers. But we can compose any $n_{rem \neq 0} \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ {which means that remainder on division is non-zero} from smaller numbers. Note that reversing Collatz conjecture ($n \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$), the only way to do so is $n*2$ after which $n_{-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$. If we can prove that for all odd numbers preceded by smaller number and smaller number is proven to work, it effectively breaks the other cycles i.e $n_{-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ can be reversed in both ways but then $(n - 1)/3$ which yields n_{-2} will always be smaller than n . If $n_{rem \neq 0} \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ can be "composed" from smaller number, we need to prove that the conjecture works for smaller number which can either be $n_{rem \neq 0} \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ and be composed from smaller number again or $n \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$. So, the only thing left to prove that Collatz Conjecture works for every odd $n \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$. Since every odd $n \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ will yield $n_{+1} \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ and already it has previously been noted that if $n \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ is abandoned, no later number will be $n \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$. Thus the Collatz conjecture works for $n \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ also.
